

INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFECT OF MWCNT FILLED EPOXY ADHESIVES IN ENHANCING THE QUALITY OF DISSIMILAR MATERIAL BONDED JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

Most adhesively bonded joints exhibit adhesive or cohesive failure i.e. failure at the adhesive/adherend interface or within the adhesive respectively. The main objective of this study is investigate the effects of the surface modification of the metal substrate accompanied by modification of the adhesive properties on the strength of adhesively bonded joints.

In this investigation, aluminium is used as the metal substrate onto which glass reinforced epoxy composite (GFRP) is bonded. Two types of surface treatments were applied to the aluminium substrates; chemical treatment and gritblasting, while the adhesive was reinforced with multi-wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs).

In particular, this work presents the mechanical characterisation of the MWCNT/epoxy adhesive, where neat resin specimens with various CNT weight fraction contents (from 0.03 % to 0.5 %) were manufactured and tested (i.e. tensile tests) in order to determine the optimum weight fraction to enhance adhesive properties. GFRP to aluminium single lap joints bonded with either pure epoxy resin or MWCNT reinforced epoxy resin, were subsequently manufactured and tested. The tests show a moderate increase of the joint strength, when MWCNTs are added into the adhesive. In addition, the comparison between different surface preparation methods shows that shotblasting produces a major improvement in adhesive strength over chemical treatment. The test results suggest that surface preparation of the substrates is one of the most critical parameters defining the structural integrity of adhesively bonded joints.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increased use of composite materials in various industries, such as aerospace, electronics, automotive, construction and sports, has increased the demands for more efficient and effective joining technologies for dissimilar materials. Due to the fundamentally different physical properties of metals and polymer composites, joining has always been a challenging process. Mechanical fastening or adhesive bonding (or a combination of both) have traditionally been used in structural design, with adhesive bonding being considered the most efficient joining technique in terms of both lightweight and efficient load transfer. However, most of the structural adhesives, such as epoxies, exhibit lower toughness than the adherends resulting in failure of the bondline, and a means of improving the adhesive properties involving reinforcement of the adhesive is an approach often adopted to improve the joint strength.

One approach for modifying the properties of the adhesive is the use of carbon nanotubes (CNTs). CNTs which were discovered by Iijima [1] in 1991, are one dimensional carbon materials whose aspect ratio is greater than 1000 (length to diameter ratio of up to 132,000,000:1) and therefore, when dispersed in a polymer matrix this results in an extremely large interfacial surface area between the matrix and the CNT filler [2]. Apart from their high Young's modulus (1.2 TPa) and tensile strength (5 - 200 GPa), carbon nanotubes also exhibit good thermal, electrical and optical properties. They have thus been extensively used as reinforcement to enhance the properties of polymeric materials. In many studies it has been reported that the addition of CNTs into a polymeric matrix leads to an improvement of a number of material properties. In [3], it was found that the average fracture toughness of 1 wt. % and 3 wt. % MWCNT/epoxy composites was greater than that of pure epoxy by 1.29 and 1.62 times respectively. Furthermore, the 0.5 wt. % MWCNT/epoxy composite fatigue lives were 10.5 and 9.3 times greater than the average fatigue life of the pure epoxy.

Moreover, there are some indications that the incorporation of various fillers within the adhesive can also increase the strength of adhesively bonded joints. Khalili et al. [4] investigated the effect of adhesive reinforcements on the lap joint properties under tension, bending, impact and fatigue. In this study, glass fibre reinforced laminates were bonded with an epoxy resin reinforced with unidirectional, chopped glass fibres (30 vol. % with fibre orientation: 0°, 45°, 90°) and micro-glass powder (20, 30, 40 vol. %). Apart from the case of 90° fibre orientation, joint strength increased when the adhesive was reinforced with either glass powder or fibres. The fatigue life increased by 125 %, the ultimate joint strength in tension increased by 72 %, the bending ultimate joint strength increased by 112 % and the impact joint strength increased by 63 %.

In [5] carbon/carbon (C/C) and carbon/carbon – silicon carbide (C/C SiC) composites were bonded with epoxy resin containing 3 wt. % of multi-wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) and pure epoxy resin. MWCNTs were found to increase the strength and toughness of the bulk adhesive, resulting to an increase of the strength in lap joints bonded with the MWCNT reinforced epoxy adhesive. Gude et al. [6] investigated the effect of the incorporation of carbon nanotubes (0.25 wt. %) and carbon nanofibres (0.5 wt. %) to an epoxy adhesive and assessed the strength and toughness of carbon fibre/epoxy composite joints. They found that both nano-reinforcements increased the fracture energy, G_{IC} , of the joints without however, affecting the lap shear strength. Carbon nanotubes also improved the interfacial shear strength between the adherend and the adhesive and prevented the crack from propagating along the adhesive layer by changing the failure mode from fully adhesive to partly cohesive. Hsiao et al. [7] investigated the effect of the inclusion of multi-wall carbon nanotubes (i.e. 1 and 5 wt. %) in epoxy resin used to bond graphite fibre/epoxy composite adherends. After adding 5 wt. % of MWCNTs into the adhesive, lap shear strength increased by 45.6 % compared to the values for pure epoxy resin adhesive. Another interesting finding was that the failure mode shifted from adhesive (along the bonding interface) for the epoxy adhesive to cohesive for the MWCNT reinforced adhesive where the graphite fibres of the adherends were fractured, and exposed.

The mechanical performance of aluminium single lap joints bonded with aluminium powder filled epoxy (10, 25, 50 wt. %) was studied in [8]. It was found that joint strength increased with the increase of the aluminium filler content and all joints failed cohesively indicating good adhesion at the metal surface. Tensile and shear properties of composites reinforced with two types of nanofillers, i.e. carbon nanotubes and alumina nanopowder (up to 15 wt. %) were studied in [9]. Carbon/fibre epoxy laminate substrates were bonded with aluminium alloy substrates using a reinforced epoxy adhesive. Both shear and tensile properties (strength and modulus) increased with the increase of the weight percentage of the nanofillers. However, a further increase of nanofillers above 10 wt. % degraded the properties. Yu et al. [10] studied the adhesion properties of carbon nanotube reinforced epoxy (i.e. 0.5, 1, 2, 3.5 and 5 wt. %) used for bonding aluminium alloy substrates. The fracture toughness of all reinforced adhesive joints increased compared to the unreinforced ones. However, the highest value was achieved for 1 wt. % and a further increase led to the decrease of the fracture toughness due to agglomeration.

In this study, a standard epoxy resin is characterised via a series of tensile tests with the aim to define an optimum CNT weight fraction resulting in improvement of its mechanical properties. Aluminium/aluminium and aluminium/GFRP single lap joints bonded with CNT reinforced epoxy resin were manufactured and tested. CNT placement and surface preparation of metal substrates are investigated in order to quantify their effect on lap shear strength and failure mode of the joint.

2. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

The characterisation of the bulk adhesive in terms of defining the optimum CNT weight fraction and achieving as uniform dispersion as possible is critical and constitutes the first part of the experimental study. Having specified the weight fractions that affect the mechanical properties of the adhesive the most, metal to metal and metal to composite single lap joints were manufactured and tested.

2.1 Reinforced Adhesive with CNTs

A two-part epoxy resin is used as matrix and multi-wall CNTs (industrial grade 99.7 %) as the reinforcement. The CNTs used in this study were supplied by Nanocyl and are produced via the Catalysed Chemical Vapour Deposition (CVD) method. The tube diameter is typically in the range of 5 nm to 50 nm and the tube length is greater than 500 nm. Some of their properties are shown in Table 1.

E (TPa)	<i>1</i>	Strain at Break (%)	<i>10</i>
Strength (GPa)	<i>10 - 60</i>	Specific Density	<i>1.3 - 2</i>

Table 1: Mechanical Properties of MWCNTs.

CNT specimens of various weight fractions, i.e. 0.03 % to 0.5 % have been manufactured using mechanical stirring and/or ultrasonic excitation or sonication method (amplitude=40 % and cycle=0.5) in order to disperse the CNTs uniformly in the matrix. The manufacturing process involves the following steps. Epoxy resin and CNTs are mechanically stirred for 5 min at 10,000 rpm followed by sonication (ultrasonic dispersion) for either 15 min or 30 min. CNT filled resin specimens without being mechanically stirred have also been manufactured to assess whether this step in the process has any effect in the dispersion and consequently on the mechanical properties. The mixture was then placed into a vacuum chamber for 20 min in order to reduce air trapped during mixing. The hardener was then added and after 5 min of hand stirring, the mixture (resin + CNTs + hardener) is degassed again for 20 min and cast into the moulds. The resin curing process involved 24 h at room temperature followed by a post-curing process of 15 h at 50°C.

2.2 Single Lap Joints

Metal to metal, i.e. aluminium/aluminium single lap joints, as well as co-cured aluminium/GFRP single lap joints were manufactured. The surface preparation of all metal substrates involved the gritblasting of the bonding area creating an average surface roughness of 7.5 µm followed by surface degreasing with acetone prior to the application of the adhesive. In addition, aluminium samples whose bonding area was subjected to a chemical treatment of etching and anodising (Forest Products Laboratory etching for 25 min and Phosphoric Acid Anodising for 25 min) were prepared. Samples

with no surface preparation (just some simple surface roughening) were also manufactured to compare the different surface preparation methods.

The metal/metal joints were prepared by applying the adhesive on the joining area and then placing them on top of each other. A simple jig and weight configuration was used for each joint in order to maintain alignment and control the adhesive thickness (ranging from 0.3 mm to 0.5 mm).

In the case of dissimilar joints, the manufacturing process is a combination of hand lay-up (HLU) and vacuum bagging process. The reinforced adhesive, which was prepared as already described, was applied onto the bonding area of the metal substrate. A layer of woven glass cloth with 0.23 mm ply thickness was laid on top and then subsequent layers were added, impregnated with pure epoxy resin by simple HLU. This procedure was repeated till 16 layers were laid up, resulting in a composite laminate of approximately 3.5 mm thickness. A vacuum bagging process was then used to remove the excess air introduced through the HLU and achieve uniform thickness along the composite laminate.

2.3 Mechanical Testing

The mechanical properties of the pure epoxy and CNT/epoxy composite were evaluated by conducting tensile tests at constant crosshead speed equal to 1 mm/min. Dogbone specimens (Figure 1) were loaded to failure and an extensometer was used to measure the axial displacement.

Figure 1: Dogbone specimen configuration.

Lap shear tests were also conducted at constant crosshead speed (1mm/min). The single lap joint configuration is shown in Figure 2. The bonding area was 25 mm x 25 mm for all lap joints.

Figure 2: Single lap joint configuration.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Adhesive Results

The results presented here are averages of three specimens per case, except for the case of 0.3 wt. % CNT (5 min + 30 min) and 0.5 wt. % CNT (30 min), where only one specimen was tested.

In Figure 3, Young's modulus is plotted against the CNT weight fraction for various lengths of sonication time.

Figure 3: Young's Modulus versus CNT weight fraction for various lengths of sonication time.

A moderate increase of the modulus was observed when CNTs were added into the adhesive for all cases. In particular, when sonication time is equal to 30 min, the results are more consistent and show higher increase in modulus. Mechanical stirring prior to sonication (i.e. 5 min + 30 min) does not appear to affect the modulus when compared to only sonication for 30 min.

In Figure 4, tensile strength is plotted against the different CNT weight fractions for sonication time durations of 15 min, 30 min and 30 min preceded by 5 min of mechanical stirring. The addition of CNTs into the resin only improves the tensile strength of the resin marginally for a CNT weight fraction of 0.1 wt. %, but it reduces it for higher weight fractions.

Figure 4: Tensile Strength versus CNT weight fraction for various lengths of sonication time.

The results also suggest that 0.3 wt. % CNT seems to be the highest weight fraction that can be achieved without decreasing the strength. Further addition of CNTs above this weight fraction results in a significant degradation of the property. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of the fracture surfaces showed that this decrease in strength was due to poor dispersion and increase of CNT agglomerated areas, as shown in Figure 5. It also suggests that a different regime of dispersion might be required for the higher weight fractions.

Figure 5: a) Fracture surface of 0.5 wt. % CNT dogbone specimen (30 min), b) agglomerated area.

3.2 Single Lap Joint Results

The lap shear strength of aluminium/aluminium joints is presented in Figure 6. The surface preparation of the metal substrate is one of the most important factors defining lap shear strength. When the only surface preparation method used is acetone degreasing, joint strength values are low and increase by 53 % and 187 %, when either etching/anodising or gritblasting is used respectively. It was found that gritblasting is the method that gives the highest lap shear strength value, therefore, it was the one used for the manufacturing of dissimilar joints.

Figure 6: Lap Shear Strength of aluminium/aluminium single lap joints versus different surface preparation methods for pure epoxy resin adhesive.

The fracture surface of the aluminium/aluminium single lap joints subjected to chemical treatment (Figure 7 a) and of those with no surface preparation (Figure 7 b) shows an irregular pattern. On the contrary, the fracture pattern is symmetric for the case of gritblasting indicating that there are no weak points along the overlap length and width with the crack initiating and propagating from both ends of the overlap (Figure 7 c).

Figure 7: Bonding area of aluminium/aluminium single lap joints: a) no surface preparation, b) etching-anodising, c) gritblasting.

Using the two aforementioned surface preparation methods, aluminium/aluminium single lap joints were bonded with a nano-reinforced adhesive. The effect on lap shear strength of the two methods and the reinforced adhesives used is plotted in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Lap Shear Strength of aluminium/aluminium single lap joints versus CNT weight fraction for different surface preparation methods.

From Figure 8, it is evident that the dominating factor in defining the joint strength is the surface preparation method. Gritblasted single lap joints gave by 32 % higher lap shear strength values when compared to the chemically treated ones. The effect of CNT weight fraction is insignificant for the chemically etched joints, whereas it shows a slight increase with weight fraction for the gritblasted ones.

Lap shear strength for GFRP/aluminium single lap joints shows a small increase when CNTs are added into the adhesive for both weight fractions studied (Figure 9). Maximum shear strength is obtained for the case of 0.1 CNT wt. % showing an increase of 14.8 %.

Figure 9: Lap Shear Strength of GFRP/aluminium single lap joints versus CNT weight fraction.

Single lap joints bonded with either pure epoxy resin (Figure 10 a) and 0.1 wt. % CNT (Figure 10 b) failed cohesively, whereas for the case of 0.3 wt. % CNT (Figure 10 c) the failure mode shifted to adhesive.

Figure 10: Bonding area of GFRP/aluminium single lap joints bonded with: a) pure epoxy resin, b) 0.1 wt. % CNT, c) 0.3 wt. % CNT.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The mechanical properties of the CNT/epoxy coupons were found to be influenced by the dispersion methods (i.e. sonication/mechanical stirring and time) and particularly the sonication time duration employed. However, it is not certain at this stage whether this result is due to agglomeration or due to the damage of CNTs caused by extended sonication. CNT weight fraction produced a moderate increase of the mechanical properties with the tensile strength decreasing for weight fractions greater than 0.3 % possibly due to agglomeration.

The incorporation of CNTs into the adhesive of the aluminium/aluminium single lap joints, had a moderate improvement of the joint strength. For the case of GFRP/aluminium single lap joints, a small

increase of the lap shear strength was obtained when CNTs were added into the adhesive for both 0.1% and 0.3% weight fractions.

The substrate surface preparation was found to be the primary parameter defining the joint strength. In particular, for the aluminium/aluminium single lap joints when the only surface preparation method employed was acetone degreasing, joint strength values were low compared to the values obtained when either etching/anodising or gritblasting (increase by 53 % and 188 % respectively) was employed. For the gritblasted joints, the moderate increase of the joint strength with the increase of CNT weight fraction suggests that CNTs can positively affect the joint integrity. However, this positive effect was only evident when the substrate surface preparation was optimised.

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